

TEACHING THE FUNDAMENTALS OF SOCIOLOGY ON THE BASIS OF DIGITALIZATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8415786>

Digitalization originates in ancient times, when the numbers “0” and “1” were opened. However, this process received its rapid development, followed by social changes, in the second half of the twentieth century. Digital revolution - the transition from analogue to digital ways of working with information and data. And it seems that in this interpretation this is technical modernization, improvement of devices. However, this is a simplified understanding, and if it were not for the colossal results of the influence of information and data on society and its functioning, then this process would remain technical. “It is digital technology that allows data to be manipulated at high speed, including when transmitted via analog (continuous) or digital communication channels (analog-to-digital / digital-to-analog conversions, coding, signal modulation / demodulation). Computers, telecommunications, Internet network services have the ability to process this digital data, which gets there thanks to the conversion (digitization, digitalization) of various types of analog signals. Then, in digital form, this data is combined by devices and programs into new formats, undergoing convergence or media convergence,” as noted by I.N. Rosina. It is obvious that new, intense changes in society and its individual components caused by digitalization have become poorly perceived, described and explained by existing sociological theories. At the same time, the emergence and rapid spread of digital technologies has significantly enhanced changes that have practically affected all spheres of people’s lives - from individual household to social and state.

Modern transforming society has not yet reached a stable state, new structures and functions have not yet acquired their final form, and theories describing industrial society are already losing their attractiveness. However, it would be incorrect to assume that the new society is some absolutely new phenomenon not connected with the past, just as the theories that will most objectively describe and explain the new state of society and the transition to it will have origins and be based on previous knowledge. The development of sociological theory, like society itself, has cause-and-effect relationships; the past lies in the new, and the past continues in the new. To understand the possibilities of the necessary sociological theory for a rapidly changing society towards digitalization, it is necessary to turn to past and existing sociological

theories, concepts, and currents of sociological thought. This approach will best suggest the possibilities of forming digital sociological theories.

Thus, the twentieth century showed that classical sociology (O. Comte, G. Spencer, M. Weber, E. Durkheim, G. Simmel) was unable to holistically describe and explain the functioning and development of industrial society. Modernist theories (M. Foucault, J. Derrida, Lyotard, etc.), which appeared as a response to the problems of classical theories, turned out to be unproductive in the face of postmodernism (J. Baudrillard, Z. Baumann, etc.). But postmodernism itself (and even post-postmodernism) failed to respond to the challenges of a society transforming towards a post-industrial future, since norms, values, social roles, and even social institutions and structures began to move, and they are moving not towards the usual established ones, but to new and sometimes incomprehensible states. It should be emphasized that the development of sociological theory was ensured, first of all, by the scientific developments of European scientists (these were not only sociologists, but also representatives of other sciences), while one or another theoretical construct dominated. Thus, O. Comte's positivism was of key importance for understanding society in the early stages of the transition from a traditional to an industrial state. It was the potential of positivist theory that made it possible for the emergence of many sociological theories and concepts.

Contemporary sociological research already contains a discussion about digital sociology. The concept of "digital sociology" (from the English digital sociology) was first presented in a scientific article in 2009. In 2010, digital sociology was described by R. Neal. In 2013, the first book was published, which defined the subject of digital sociology. The book "Digital Sociology" was published in 2015. The first scientific conference on digital sociology was held in New York in 2015. This subject area has been described as "a sub-discipline that focuses on understanding the use of digital media as part of everyday life, and how these various technologies contribute to human behavior patterns, social relationships and the concept of self-government."

Although the term "digital sociology" has not yet fully entered scientific use, sociologists have been involved in research related to the Internet since its inception. First of all, sociologists became interested in problems associated with online communities, cyberspace and cyberculture. These studies stimulated the emergence of various fields of sociological knowledge, which received names such as "cybersociology", "sociology of the Internet", "sociology of online communities", "sociology of social media", "sociology of cyberculture", etc.

It is important to emphasize that the authors of works on digital sociology rightly consider the above concepts to be too narrow, fragmented and have insufficient sociological potential. And, conversely, digital sociology embraces the above and other digital approaches, describes and explains digital social objects, phenomena and processes that constitute a relatively independent, special sphere of social life.

The emergence of digital sociology was preceded by other digital subdisciplines, most notably digital humanities and digital anthropology. They influenced the development of the theoretical framework and subject field of digital sociology, including the following sections:

- professional digital practice;
- sociological analysis of the use of digital media;
- analysis of digital data;
- critical digital sociology;
- public digital sociology.

N. Mares expanded her understanding of digital sociology, including in the subject area the problems of new opportunities for social monitoring, analysis of digital opportunities for intervention in social life, new forms of observation and control, as well as the creation of new knowledge about social reality. At the same time, existing ideas about digital sociology do not provide an unambiguous understanding of its theoretical sources and foundations. To a certain extent, the theories of post-industrialism, information society, informatization, information determinism and information technology, and, of course, digitalization can be considered the theoretical origins and foundations.

Next, an attempt is made to present in a generalized form the possible theoretical origins and foundations of digital sociology. Obviously, it is logical to consider theoretical constructs, starting with post-industrialism, information society, theories of informatization, information technology and other private information studies. It should be noted that such a division is conditional, and it serves only as a methodological tool that allows us to trace the progress of the emergence of sociological theories and approaches as predecessors of digital sociology. However, for a more in-depth understanding of digital sociology, it is necessary to explore the relationship between technical and natural science theories in conjunction with the social consequences of digitalization in its initial understanding.

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